

ISic4338

I.Sicily inscription 4338

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Comiso

Provenance

Cifali-Ganzari (? 37.06333, 14.68609 for Ganzeria)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Camarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Di Stefano, G. 2013. Camarina. Le acquisizioni, il museo tematico, la collezione "Biagio Pace", il lapidario. Ispica. At 33

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic4338. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4390336>